

Composition and Stability of the Interaction Product of Cu(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) with 2-Benzofuryl Phenyl Ketoxime in Methanolic Medium

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The composition of Cu(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) complexes with 2-benzofuryl phenyl ketoxime in methanolic medium has been determined conductometrically and pH-metrically as 1 : 1 for Cu(II) and 1 : 2 for Fe(III), Cu(II) and Co(II) complexes. The values of stability constants (log K) are 19.5 for $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, 13.35 for $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ and 9.92 for $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$. These complexes have been isolated in solid form and their composition also established by analysis.

The reaction products of 2-benzofuryl phenyl ketoxime with metals are unstable in aqueous medium but they can be stabilised if the reactions are carried out in methanolic solutions. Survey of the existing literature reveals that nothing has been done to elucidate the composition and stability of its metal complexes. The present paper deals with our study of the complexes formed with Cu(II), Co(II) and Fe(III).

Preliminary observations gave the following results: (i) Copper gave a buff coloured precipitate with oxime at pH 6.0 and a dark green coloured precipitate at pH 9.0, (ii) the pH for the onset of precipitation of the cobalt complex (green colour) and ferric complex (yellow colour) was from 8 to 10.

The composition and stability of these complexes using pH metric and conductometric technique was determined. The isolation and analysis of the complexes was also carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and Solutions : 2-Benzofuryl phenyl ketoxime (M.P. $128^\circ \pm 1^\circ$) was prepared in the pure form by the interaction of 2-benzoyl benzofuran, hydroxyl amine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in ethanol¹ in the laboratory. A.R. quality cupric chloride, cobaltous nitrate, ferric chloride and potassium hydroxide were employed in the preparation of standard solutions. Fe(III) was determined by reduction with stannous chloride and subsequent titration with a solution of dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator, and cobalt and copper gravimetrically as anthranilate and thiocyanate respectively.

All the solutions were prepared in 80% methanol.

Apparatus : pH-measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter model H with a glass electrode which had been cleaned thoroughly with dilute acid and allowed to stand

in methanol for several days before use^{2,3}. The pH meter was standardised using potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer of pH 4.0. Conductance measurements were done with the help of a Philips conductivity bridge, PR 9500.

All the experiments were performed at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

pH-metric and conductometric titrations: 10 ml. of 0.01M oxime was titrated pH-metrically with 0.1M KOH. The equivalent of base added per equivalent of the ligand came out to be one and the reaction can be represented as

In the case of both, pH-metry and conductometry, direct (20 ml. and 40 ml. of metal ion of conc. 0.005M and 0.0025M in the cell) and reverse (10 and 20 ml. of ligand of conc. 0.02M and 0.01M in the cell) titrations were carried out. The solution of ligand was prepared in one equivalent of methanolic KOH to give the potassium salt of oxime ($C_{15}H_{10}O_2NK$). The combining ratios obtained by both the methods were 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 corresponding to Cu(II) : oxime; 1 : 2 corresponding to Co(II) : oxime and 1 : 2 corresponding to Fe(III) : oxime. The reaction can be represented by the following equation :

where X = Cl or NO₃.

Isolation and analysis: (i) $[Cu(C_{15}H_{10}O_2N)(OH)(H_2O)]$ was prepared by mixing the methanolic solution of cupric chloride and oxime in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 6.0 by the addition of KOH to get a buff coloured precipitate. For analysis, the compound was treated with glacial acetic acid and copper estimated as cuprous thiocyanate, (Found : Cu, 18.8%; N, 4.09%; Calc : Cu, 18.9%; N, 4.18%).

(ii) $[Cu(C_{15}H_{10}O_2N)_2]$ was prepared by mixing the reactants containing a little excess of oxime over the calculated amount in order to get the 1 : 2 complex which was dark green in colour. The pH of the mixture was maintained at 9.5 by the addition of KOH. The method of isolation and analysis was the same as in the case of first compound. (Found : Cu, 11.75%; N, 5.0%; Calc. Cu, 11.86%; N, 5.2%).

(iii) $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ was prepared by mixing the reactants in the same way as in the preparation of complex (II) and adjusting the $p\text{H} \approx 9.0$. (Found : Co, 10.96%; N, 5.08%; Calc. Co, 11.10%; N, 5.27%).

(iv) $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ was prepared by mixing the ferric chloride and oxime in the same way as in the preparation of complex (II) and (III) and adjusting the $p\text{H} \approx 9.0$. (Found : Fe, 9.80%; N, 4.86%; Calc. Fe, 9.91%; N, 4.97%).

Nonpolymerisation of the metal ions in methanolic medium : The nonpolymerisation of ferric ion in methanolic medium has been reported earlier⁴. The same experiments were performed with Cu(II) and Co(II) ions which showed that these ions also do not polymerise throughout the $p\text{H}$ range 3 to 12.

Dissociation constant of the ligand (2-benzofuryl phenyl-Ketoxime) : Its dissociation constant may be represented as follows :

$$K^* = \frac{(\text{R}^-)(\text{H}^+)}{(\text{RH})}$$

The constant is determined by measuring the $p\text{H}$ values of the solution resulting from progressive addition of a standard alkali to a reagent solution of known strength and from the formation curve, obtained by plotting $n\text{H}$ against $p\text{H}$ values (Fig. 1) where $n\text{H}$ = average number of hydrogen ions attached to ligand ion.

$$n\text{H} = \frac{\text{RH}}{\text{R}^- + \text{RH}} = \frac{\text{R}^- - \text{P} - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}^-}{\text{R}^-}$$

where R = total concentration of the reagent, and P = concentration of alkali added.

The correct value of pK^* was obtained as $p\text{H}$ from the curve (Fig. 1) when $n\text{H} = 0.5$. Thus the value of pK^* was found to be 11.65.

Fig. 1. 20.0 ml of 0.02M oxime titrated with 0.01M KOH.

Stability of the complexes : It was determined by Bjerrum's method. Titration of the ligand (20 ml. of 0.02M) with and without metal ion (2 ml. of 0.02M) was performed against KOH (0.1M). The values of \bar{n} , average number of ligand bound per metal ion

were evaluated and were plotted against the corresponding value of $-\log R$. These values of \bar{n} were corrected by Bjerrum's method⁵ of successive approximations and were then again plotted against $-\log R$. The curve for copper is given in Fig. 2. Similar types of curves were obtained for Co(II) and Fe(III). The values of $\log K$ obtained from these

curves are given in the following table :

TABLE 1
Values of $\log K$ of different complexes

Complexes	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K$	$-\Delta F$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	7.35	6.00	13.35	18.44
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	5.08	4.84	9.92	13.70
$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	11.00	8.50	19.50	26.94

The values of $-\Delta F$ were calculated from the equation $\Delta F = -RT \ln K$ where the terms have their usual significance. The values of stability constants ($\log K$) are 19.5, 13.35 and 9.92 for Fe(III), Cu(II) and Co(II) complexes respectively; hence it is concluded that the complexing properties of these metals with 2-benzofuryl phenyl ketoxime are in the order $\text{Fe(III)} > \text{Cu(II)} > \text{Co(II)}$.

Since the $p\text{H}$ scale was described only for aqueous solutions, this study was carried out in 80% methanolic medium; all these constants may be considered as arbitrary values.

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